

This electronic companion is part of the manuscript entitled “A Clearing Mechanism for Joint Energy and Ancillary Services in Non-Convex Markets Considering High Penetration of Renewable Energy Sources”, which contains three appendices. Appendix A presents the dual formulation for the proposed SCUC problem. Appendix B linearizes the bilinear terms in the main paper using binary representation, and the details of data of case studies are brought in Appendix C.

APPENDIX A: DUAL FORMULATION OF PRIMAL STOCHASTIC SECURITY-CONSTRAINED UNIT COMMITMENT PROBLEM

Since (4a) is nonlinear, it should be linearized as follows:

$$(v_{it\omega} - y_{it\omega}) P_i^{Min} \leq P_{it\omega}^n \leq 10RR_i^{res} (v_{it\omega} + z_{it}); (\rho_{it\omega}^{fs1}, \rho_{it\omega}^{fs2}); \quad \forall i \in I_F, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (8a)$$

$$y_{it\omega} \leq z_{it}; \rho_{it\omega}^{yz}; \quad \forall i \in I_F, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (8b)$$

$$y_{it\omega} \leq v_{it\omega}; \rho_{it\omega}^{yv}; \quad \forall i \in I_F, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (8c)$$

$$y_{it\omega} \in \{0, 1\}; \quad \forall i \in I_F, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (8d)$$

where, (8d) should be relaxed as below.

$$0 \leq y_{it\omega} \leq 1; (\varrho_{it\omega}^{yMin}, \varrho_{it\omega}^{yMax}); \quad \forall i \in I_F, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (8e)$$

In the following, the dual formulation of the primal LP, which is obtained from linearizing the stochastic SCUC problem, is represented.

$$\begin{aligned} & \max \sum_{i \in T} \left[\sum_{l \in L} \left(\lambda_{it} D_{it} + \sum_{l, m \in M_l} (-f_{lm}^{Max} (\xi_{lmt}^{Min} + \xi_{lmt}^{Max})) \right) \right. \\ & + \lambda_{it}^d D_{it}^d + \lambda_{it}^u D_{it}^u + \lambda_{it}^s (D_{it}^u + D_{it}^s) + \lambda_{it}^n (D_{it}^u + D_{it}^s + D_{it}^n) \\ & + \sum_{i \in I} (\mu_{it}^{n,Min} P_i^{Min} - \mu_{it}^{n,Max} RR_i^{n,Max} - 10RR_i^{res} \beta_{it} - \gamma_{it} P_i^{Max} \\ & - \delta_{it}^{Min} RR_i^{op} - \delta_{it}^{Max} RR_{it}^{op} - \sigma_{it}^{Max}) + \sum_{l \in L} \sum_{q \in Q_l} \sum_{\omega} \varphi_{lt\omega} W_{qt\omega} \\ & + \sum_{q \in Q} \left(-\mu_{qt}^{W,Max} W_q^{Max} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \rho_{qt\omega}^{spill} W_{qt\omega} \right) \\ & \left. + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} (-\varrho_{it\omega}^{Max} - \varrho_{it\omega}^{yMax}) + \sum_{l, m \in M_l} \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} -f_{lm}^{Max} (\varpi_{lmt\omega}^{Min} + \varpi_{lmt\omega}^{Max}) \right] \\ & + \sum_{i \in I} (-\mu_{i1}^{SU} z_0 K_i^{SU} + \delta_{i1}^{Min} P_{i0} - \delta_{i1}^{Max} P_{i0}), \quad (9a) \end{aligned}$$

subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} & \vartheta_{1|_{\eta=1}} + \sum_{m \in M_l} B_{lm} \left[\xi_{lmt}^{Max} - \xi_{mnt}^{Max} - \xi_{lmt}^{Min} + \xi_{mnt}^{Min} - (\lambda_{lt} - \lambda_{mt}) \right. \\ & \left. - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} (\varphi_{lt\omega} - \varphi_{mt\omega}) \right]; \quad \forall l, \forall t, \quad (9b) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \vartheta_{1|_{\omega=1}} + \sum_{m \in M_l} B_{lm} \left(\varpi_{lmt\omega}^{Max} - \varpi_{mnt\omega}^{Max} - \varpi_{lmt\omega}^{Min} + \varpi_{mnt\omega}^{Min} \right. \\ & \left. - (\varphi_{lt\omega} - \varphi_{mt\omega}) \right) \geq 0; \quad \forall l, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (9c) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & C_i - \lambda_{it} - \mu_{it}^{P,Min} + \mu_{it}^{P,Max} - \alpha_{it} + \gamma_{it} - \delta_{it}^{Min} + \delta_{i,t+1}^{Min} + \delta_{it}^{Max} \\ & - \delta_{i,t+1}^{Max} = 0; \quad \forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \forall t, \quad (9d) \end{aligned}$$

$$1 - \mu_{it}^{SU0} - \mu_{it}^{SU} = 0; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \quad (9e)$$

$$C_i^d - \lambda_{it}^d + \mu_{it}^{d,Max} - \mu_{it}^{d,Min} + \alpha_{it} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \rho_{it\omega}^{d,Max} = 0;$$

$$\forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \forall t, \quad (9f)$$

$$C_i^u - \lambda_{it}^u - \lambda_{it}^s - \lambda_{it}^n + \mu_{it}^{u,Max} - \mu_{it}^{u,Min} + \beta_{it} + \gamma_{it} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \rho_{it\omega}^{u,Max} = 0; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \quad (9g)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & C_i^n - \lambda_{it}^n - \mu_{it}^{n,Min} + \mu_{it}^{n,Max} + \beta_{it} + \gamma_{it} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Max1} \\ & - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Max} = 0; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \quad (9h) \end{aligned}$$

$$C_i^s - \lambda_{it}^s - \lambda_{it}^n - \mu_{it}^{s,Min} + \mu_{it}^{s,Max} + \beta_{it} + \gamma_{it} - \sum_{\omega} \rho_{it\omega}^{s,Max} = 0; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (9i)$$

$$\rho_{it\omega}^{d,Max} - \pi_{\omega} C_i - \varphi_{lt\omega} - \rho_{it\omega}^{d,Min} = 0; \quad \forall t, \forall \omega, \forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \quad (9j)$$

$$\pi_{\omega} C_i + \varphi_{lt\omega} - \rho_{it\omega}^{u,Min} + \rho_{it\omega}^{u,Max} = 0; \quad \forall t, \forall \omega, \forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \quad (9k)$$

$$\pi_{\omega} C_i + \varphi_{lt\omega} - \rho_{it\omega}^{s,Min} + \rho_{it\omega}^{s,Max} = 0; \quad \forall t, \forall \omega, \forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \quad (9l)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi_{\omega} C_i + \pi_{\omega} \varphi_{lt\omega} - \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Min1} + \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Max1} - \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Min} + \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Max} - \rho_{it\omega}^{fs1} \\ & + \rho_{it\omega}^{fs2} = 0; \quad \forall t, \forall \omega, \forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \quad (9m) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi_{\omega} K_i^{SU} - \rho_{it\omega}^{fs1} P_i^{Min} - 10RR_i^{res} \rho_{it\omega}^{fs2} + \rho_{it\omega}^{yv} = 0; \\ & \quad \forall t, \forall \omega, \forall l, \forall i \in I_l, \quad (9n) \end{aligned}$$

$$-\lambda_{it} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \varphi_{lt\omega} + \mu_{qt}^{W,Max} - \mu_{qt}^{W,Min} \geq 0; \quad \forall t, \forall \omega; \forall l, \forall q \in I_q, \quad (9o)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\mu_{it}^{P,Min} P_i^{Min} - \mu_{it}^{P,Max} P_i^{Max} + (\mu_{it}^{SU} - \mu_{i,t+1}^{SU}) K_i^{SU} - \mu_{it}^{d,Max} RR_i^d \\ & - \mu_{it}^{u,Max} RR_i^u - \mu_{it}^{s,Max} RR_i^s + \sigma_{it}^{Max} - \sigma_{it}^{Min} - \mu_{it}^{n,Min} P_i^{Min} \\ & + \alpha_{it} P_i^{Min} - \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} (\rho_{it\omega}^{n,Max} + \rho_{it\omega}^{fs2}) 10RR_i^{res} + \rho_{it\omega}^{yz} = 0; \end{aligned}$$

$$\forall i \in I_{Th}, \forall t, \quad (9p)$$

$$-\varphi_{lt\omega} + \rho_{qt\omega}^{spill} \geq 0; \quad \forall q, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (9q)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -P_i^{Min} \rho_{it\omega}^{n,Min} - P_i^{Min} \rho_{it\omega}^{fs1} + \rho_{it\omega}^{yz} + \rho_{it\omega}^{yv} - \varrho_{it\omega}^{yMin} + \varrho_{it\omega}^{yMax} \geq 0; \\ & \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall \omega, \quad (9r) \end{aligned}$$

where, all $\xi, \lambda, \sigma, \mu, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \gamma, \rho, \varpi, \vartheta$ are either equal or greater than zero.

APPENDIX B: SOLVING THE BILINEAR MODEL THROUGH THE DISCRETIZATION PROCEDURE

Consider a term including the product of two continuous variables A and B . To linearize using binary representation, the variable A should be represented by a series of binary variables $h_k \in \{0, 1\}$ as presented in (10).

$$A = \bar{A} \sum_{k=0}^K 2^{-k} h_k + err, \quad (10)$$

here, \bar{A} is either equal or greater than $A/2$, K is the number of required binary variables and determines the approximation accuracy. Whenever K is large enough, err can be ignored. Then, the product of A and B can be rewritten as (11a)-(11c).

$$A \times B = \bar{A} \sum_{k=0}^K 2^{-k} U_k. \quad (11a)$$

$$0 \leq B - U_k \leq G(1 - h_k); \quad \forall k, \quad (11b)$$

$$0 \leq U_k \leq Gh_k; \quad \forall k, \quad (11c)$$

in which, G is a large positive number to ensure that if $h_k = 1$, the value of auxiliary variable U_k becomes equal to B and otherwise, U_k would be zero. Based on the above formulation, the linearization details of the profit insurance constraint have been calculated in the rest of this appendix.

The first nonlinear term is linearized as (12a)-(12c).

$$P_{it} = \sum_{k=0}^K h_{itk} \hat{P}_k; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \quad (12a)$$

$$0 \leq \lambda_t - u_{itk} \leq G(1 - h_{itk}); \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall k, \quad (12b)$$

$$0 \leq u_{itk} \leq Gh_{itk}; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall k, \quad (12c)$$

where, h_{itk} is an auxiliary variable, $\hat{P}_k = 2^k$, and K must be determined such that 2^K is greater than half of the maximum capacity of the largest generating unit of the system. This value for K ensures that the approximation can cover all available amounts of feasible dispatches. By increasing the value of K , the approximation becomes more accurate.

By applying the binary representation to approximate P_{it} , the continuous production of P_{it} and λ_t can be replaced by $\sum_k h_{itk} \hat{P}_k$. Similarly, the binary representation for second nonlinear term is as (13a)-(13g).

$$R_{it}^x = \sum_{b \in BA} h_{itb}^x \hat{R}_{it}^x; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall x, \quad (13a)$$

$$0 \leq \Lambda_t^x - u_{itb}^x \leq G(1 - h_{itb}^x); \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall b, \forall x, \quad (13b)$$

$$0 \leq u_{itb}^x \leq Gh_{itb}^x; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall b, \forall x, \quad (13c)$$

$$\Lambda_t^d = \lambda_t^d; \quad \forall t, \quad (13d)$$

$$\Lambda_t^u = \lambda_t^u + \lambda_t^s + \lambda_t^n; \quad \forall t, \quad (13e)$$

$$\Lambda_t^s = \lambda_t^s + \lambda_t^n; \quad \forall t, \quad (13f)$$

$$\Lambda_t^n = \lambda_t^n; \quad \forall t, \quad (13g)$$

where, $x \in \{d, u, s, n\}$.

Similar to the scheduled powers and ancillary services, the deployed powers should be approximated as (14a)-(14c) to linearize the third nonlinear term.

$$P_{it\omega}^{dx} = \sum_{b \in BA} h_{it\omega b}^{dx} \hat{P}_{it}^{dx}; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall x, \quad (14a)$$

$$0 \leq \pi_{\omega} \varphi_{it\omega} - u_{it\omega b}^{dx} \leq G(1 - h_{it\omega b}^{dx}); \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall b, \forall \omega, \forall x, \quad (14b)$$

$$0 \leq u_{it\omega b}^{dx} \leq Gh_{it\omega b}^{dx}; \quad \forall i, \forall t, \forall b, \forall \omega, \forall x. \quad (14c)$$

Using the binary representation for the discretization of the scheduled powers, scheduled ancillary services, and deployed powers, the profit insurance condition for joint energy and deployment reserve can be linearized as below:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i \in T} \left[\left(\sum_{k=0}^K u_{itk} \hat{P}_k - C_i P_{it} - C_i^{SU} \right) + \sum_{b \in BA} \left(\hat{R}_b^u u_{itb}^u + \hat{R}_b^s u_{itb}^s \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \hat{R}_b^n u_{itb}^n - \hat{R}_b^d u_{itb}^d \right) - \sum_{b \in BA} \left(C_b^u R_{it}^u + C_b^s R_{it}^s + C_b^n R_{it}^n - C_b^d R_{it}^d \right) \right] \\ & + \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \left[\sum_{b \in BA} \left(-\hat{P}_b^{dd} u_{it\omega b}^{dd} + \hat{P}_b^{du} u_{it\omega b}^{du} + \hat{P}_b^{ds} u_{it\omega b}^{ds} + \hat{P}_b^{dn} u_{it\omega b}^{dn} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\left. - \pi_{\omega} C_i \left(P_{it\omega}^{du} + P_{it\omega}^{ds} + P_{it\omega}^{dn} - P_{it\omega}^{dd} \right) - \pi_{\omega} v_{it\omega} K_i^{SU} \right] \geq 0; \quad \forall i. \quad (15a)$$

APPENDIX C: PHYSICAL AND ECONOMIC DATA OF THE GENERATING UNITS

A. 3 Bus Data

This test network is shown in Fig. 6. The reactances of all transmission lines are considered equal to 0.13 per unit and their maximum capacities are equal to 200 MW.

Fig. 6: A test network with 3 buses.

Table IV represents the physical and economic data of the generating units and RES.

TABLE IV: Technical data of generating units and RES.

Unit	K_i^{SU}	P_i^{Max}	P_i^{Min}	C_i	$C_i^{d/u}$	C_i^s	C_i^n
G_1	101.1	95	10	20.03	2.03	1.015	0.812
G_2	103.2	100	10	50.06	5.06	2.503	2.0024
G_3	2001.06	105	10	10.01	1.001	0.5005	0.4004
W	-	120	0	-	-	-	-

All generating units G_1 , G_2 , and G_3 can provide different kinds of ancillary services (regulation down/up, spinning, and non-spinning reserves) up to 20 MW. Thus, RR_i^d , RR_i^u , RR_i^s , and RR_i^n are considered equal to 20 MW/h. In addition, RR_i^{res} and RR_i^{pp} for all generating units are considered equal to P_i^{Max} .

B. 118 Bus Data

To linearize the cost functions, the quadratic costs of generating units are approximated by one piece of line. A linear cost function is considered for ancillary services as a fraction of energy cost, which is presented in Table V.

TABLE V: Ancillary services costs and demands.

Ancillary services	Marginal cost	Demand
Regulation Down	$0.10 C_i$	$0.05 D$
Regulation Up	$0.10 C_i$	$0.05 D$
Spinning Reserve	$0.05 C_i$	$0.04 D$
Non-spinning Reserve	$0.04 C_i$	$0.10 D$

Here, C_i is the energy cost of generating unit i and D is the total demand. It is assumed that the generating units bid their related marginal costs for energy and ancillary services truthfully. As it can be observed, the faster ancillary services, e.g., regulation up, are more expensive than the slower ones, e.g., spinning reserve. The total demand of the network is considered equal to 4200 MW.